

Advanced Construction Progress Management with BEXEL Manager

IURI GONÇALVES RODRIGUES

Supervisors:

Tomo Cerovšek

Faculty of Civil and Geodetic Engineering, University of Ljubljana, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Veljko Janjić

BEXEL Consulting, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Abstract

The digitalization of the construction sector is seen by several international organs and policy makers as inevitable and vital for the Architecture, Engineering and Construction Industry prosperity and sustainability. Its benefits span from the enhancement of current practices to the integration of disruptive tools and technologies allowing the emergence of new and improved processes. The progress management process is an essential part of the construction projects that analysis and manages the performance of works developed proving to be key in avoiding time and costs overrun, delivering projects efficiently.

One of the main aspects of efficient project management that enables an accurate process of decision making is the ability to analyse as-built and as-planned progress information discrepancies and communicate it in a clear way. This study focuses on exploring the automation of construction progress management by identifying new technologies and methods of retrieving and use information required, and how to process this information to analyse earned value and delays of the construction project in an ongoing manner, controlling its performance, and taking advantage of the integration of Building Information Modeling (BIM), project management tools and software.

The dissertation includes the design of a framework using BIM and the project management software Bexel Manager to manage the construction progress and applies it to a use-case scenario to ultimately assess it in terms of costs and times performance through key performance indicators (KPI).

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/vIgg0eX3rQg>

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